

Collaboration Area Call: Best Practices

Overview

This guide provides an overview of best practices for running calls for your ESIP Collaboration Area (i.e., Cluster or Committee). This resource was developed by the [2025 Community Fellows cohort](#) in collaboration with ESIP staff.

Learn To:

- Increase call attendance
- Engage existing and new members
- Disseminate resources

Best Practices

General

- **Raise awareness of group activities:** ESIP is always onboarding new community members. Make sure all members of the ESIP community know what your group is currently doing and how to participate. Use ESIP-wide communication channels as appropriate (e.g., ESIP Newsletter, esip-all mailing list, #general Slack channel). Ensure your group's webpage content is up to date so anyone interested in your Collaboration Area knows how to engage.
 - **Pro Tip:** Bookmark links to your notes document, webpage, YouTube playlist, and how to join your mailing list in your Slack channel.

- **Minimize cancellations:** You want to minimize call cancellations as this will discourage participation. If you have had >3 cancellations in one year that are not due to holidays or conferences, your Collaboration Area may want to consider joining another Collaboration Area or going on hiatus.
 - **Resource:** [How to Cluster in ESIP](#) to learn more about hiatus status
- **Create a shared vocabulary:** Consider creating a shared glossary of common terms and acronyms for helping everyone, especially new members, easily follow discussions.

Preparation: Announcing a Call

A Month Before

- **Check for conflicts:** Maintain awareness of upcoming holidays or conferences / events that will impact community participation.
 - **Resource:** [Holiday Calendar](#)
- **Canceling or rescheduling upcoming calls:** [Notify staff](#) if you need to reschedule or cancel an upcoming call as early as possible so staff can make updates to the Community Calendar. You will also need to send messages out via your communication channels to notify members of the change.
- **Draft an agenda:** Communications should start going out at least one week before a scheduled call. Start as early as possible with drafting an agenda.
 - **Pro Tip:** If your agenda includes discussion or conversation, identify time constraints, and make sure that the goal of the conversation remains at the forefront. Discussion questions should align directly with the goal(s).

A Week Before

- **Send reminders:** Send multiple reminders of upcoming calls through your communications channels (e.g., mailing list, Slack). We recommend at least two reminders: one week in advance and the day of the call. You can write and schedule emails and Slack posts as a follow-up task after each meeting so you do not forget.
 - **Pro Tip:** Create email templates that you can re-use for every call.
- **Share information on how to join the call:** Over time, ESIP has changed the way someone can sign up to attend an upcoming call. Do not assume that everyone is aware of how to join. Remind them that they need to register on the event page at least a day in advance and share the appropriate community calendar event link.
- **Share an agenda:** An agenda helps members of your Collaboration Area decide if they are interested in participating. If the topic is one that any ESIP member can attend, we recommend you also share through ESIP-wide communication channels.

- **Pro Tip:** Be creative in identifying a no-agenda call format that will allow you to easily fill the gaps when needed. For example, you can lead a networking activity or just play an online game. We all need a break from time to time so don't worry about leading calls that focus on coming together to connect and take a break from the day-to-day. Networking and building community is an important part of what ESIP does.
- **Resource:** [Drawasaurus](#) is an online game where you can create a list of items for participants to draw. You can make these specific to your Collaboration Area. There are also tools out there to generate your own [Jeopardy board](#).

Implementation: Running a Call

Joining

- **Sign in early:** Sign into your [Collaboration Area's dedicated Zoom room](#) at least five minutes before the call starts. Be sure to select and start the recurring meeting designated for your Collaboration Area and do not simply "start a new meeting" as that will be a different Zoom space.

Starting

- **Reference the Community Participation Guidelines:** These guidelines are meant to create collaborative spaces that are inclusive, outlining acceptable and unacceptable behaviors. Mentioning them and [posting a link to them](#) at the beginning of a call demonstrates their importance to our community and the spaces we operate in.
 - **Pro Tip:** Have links you plan to post in the chat easily accessible so you can post them quickly in the chat.
- **Assign co-hosts:** Once you are on the call, depending on who joins the room first, make sure ESIP staff, Collaboration Area chairs, and the Community Fellow are co-hosts so they have access to host features.
- **Remove AI bots:** Do not allow AI notetaking bots to stay in the room if you do not have permission/consent from everyone attending. If someone needs an AI to attend for whatever reason, they should request permission from the Chair beforehand and consent should be given by all attendees prior to starting the meeting.
- **Designate a notetaker:** It is difficult to facilitate a call while also taking notes. If you have a community member who regularly attends meetings, you may want to designate them as a notetaker. Or, you may wish to ask prior to each meeting if someone is willing to serve in that role. The notetaker does not need to take exhaustive notes, but they should capture key takeaways, decisions that were

made, and any action items. Basically, enough information should be captured so that someone who did not attend knows what happened at the meeting.

- **Pro Tip:** Have a backup notetaker to jump in if the notetaker is speaking. It usually works well to have this individual be the call facilitator.
- **Resource:** [TEMPLATE_Cluster Notes](#)
- **Welcome new members:** If someone new is joining the group, ask them to introduce themselves. If there is space in the agenda and not too many people joining the call, ask everyone to briefly introduce themselves or at least state their name and affiliation before the first time they speak so new participants can get to know existing members.
 - **Pro Tip:** Remain aware that everyone likes to contribute in different ways. Give them opportunities to speak or write in chat, whatever their preference. They may also wish to only observe and that is okay too. You can ask for contributions by stating, "if you are comfortable doing so, please introduce yourself by unmuting or posting an introduction in the chat".
- **Ask permission to record:** If you want to record the call, ask permission to record before starting the recording. Be explicit about where the recording will be shared (e.g., Collaboration Area folder, YouTube).
 - **Pro Tip:** If a recording will be posted on YouTube or another public location, you can indicate that participants may want to turn off their cameras or rename themselves before the recording starts.
- **Share upcoming news and announcements:** The ESIP staff member can share ESIP-wide news but other attendees should be asked if they have anything to share before jumping into the agenda. This raises community awareness of community-adjacent activities and events of interest.

During

- **Encourage participation:** During times of discussion, inform attendees to use the raise hand feature if they want to speak or to post questions and comments in the chat. Acknowledge messages posted in the chat to ensure they are considered as part of the discussion.
- **Distribute contributions:** Moderate speaking time to ensure everyone has an opportunity to add their input. If 1-2 individuals continue to raise their hand to speak, make sure you provide space for others. For example, "before I call on [name] again, is there anyone else who has something to add?"
 - **Pro Tip:** Don't be afraid of a long pause with no one speaking. This allows everyone some time to think and reflect before they decide they have something to share.
 - **Pro Tip:** Use a Q&A queue to acknowledge questions in the order they are raised.

- **Pro Tip:** Add a 5-minute reflection time prior to starting a discussion. This provides quiet time for everyone to draft responses to a question before opening it up to discussion. It also provides content for jump starting the conversation.
- **Use collaborative tools:** ESIP has access to collaborative tools you may want to use for a call to make conversations more engaging. They are commonly used for our meetings, but they are available for Collaboration Area calls as well.
 - **Resource:** [Slido](#)
 - **Resource:** [Miro](#)

Ending

- **Announce the next call:** Include the date / time and topic (if known). This encourages people to add the next event to their calendar and demonstrates that the Collaboration Area collaborates consistently.
 - **Pro Tip:** Before the call starts, add the date and time of next meeting and link to register at bottom of notes document so you can reference that at the end of the call.
- **Review and reflect:** Review any action items brought up during the call. Spend time reflecting on whether or not you achieved the goals for your meeting.
- **Say thanks:** Share your appreciation with those who presented, those who attended, and for all contributions to the meeting.
- **Record call information:** After each call, ESIP staff record a 1-2 sentence call summary, number of participants, and whether or not you have slides or a recording in the Collaboration Area Information spreadsheet. If an ESIP staff member is not on your call, you should capture this information.

Follow Up: After the Call

- **Share content publicly:** Presentations and recordings of presentations are outputs that can be shared through public platforms. Consider depositing presentation slides in Zenodo or posting presentations on ESIP's YouTube channel for wider reach.
- **Show appreciation:** If a guest speaker presented for your Collaboration Area, consider following up with a note, thanking them for their contribution and sharing any positive feedback you received from those who participated. Consider sharing appreciation in public forums like social media.

Accessibility Considerations

Note: These considerations were developed by The Carpentries under a CC-BY license.

Fonts and Color

- Use simple fonts like Inter, Sans Serif, Calibri, Arial, Verdana, and Times New Roman
- Ensure significant color contrast between text and backgrounds; test with the [Contrast Checker](#)
- Use more than color to communicate information
- When possible avoid these color combinations green/red, green/brown, blue/purple, green/blue, light green/yellow, blue/grey, green/grey, green/black

Slide Design

- Minimize text on slide to prevent overcrowding
- Outline session content in an introductory slide so the audience knows what to expect
- Use large, simple charts and tables

Images and Video

- Use SVG file for images
- Images need to be high resolution
- All videos should be captioned
- Avoid flashing content and excessive animations
- All images should include [alt.text](#)

Delivery

- Do not speak too fast
- Give attendees time to process information by pausing between topics and after you ask for questions
- Use a headset for higher quality audio
- Explain charts and tables verbally; do not just reference them
- Any group work should be written out and displayed during work time so audience can refer back to it

Content

- Share presentation materials in advance with participants
- Use plain text; spell out acronyms and avoid or define technical terms, jargon, and idioms Save documents as .docx format to preserve accessibility features. Other formats by Microsoft Word (RTF, DOC, TXT, and ODF) may not be accessible.
- Image based PDFs are inaccessible.
- Check your document for accessibility. [Microsoft Suite](#), [PDF](#), [Google Docs add-on](#)